

EFFECTS OF TEMPERATURE ON STATIC AND FATIGUE STRENGTH OF WIND TURBINE COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In this work, a glass/epoxy material system, which is representative for wind turbine blade design, was used to evaluate the effect of temperature on its mechanical behaviour in terms of stiffness and strength. In order to understand these effects, it is important to describe and analyse the relevant damage mechanisms, such as physical ageing and thermal stresses. Test data is presented and analysed from strength and fatigue experiments on shelf-aged 6 years old material, as well as thermally aged material. For comparison, a selection of test standards was used to obtain material properties. Specimens extracted from panels manufactured between 2007 and 2014 are used to evaluate the effect of ageing during storage, after isothermal exposure and after thermal (shock) cycling. These results were compared with reference data obtained from tests performed either shortly after manufacturing or without additional conditioning. DSC measurements were performed to evaluate the effect of ageing on the T_g and enthalpy relaxation. For specimens tested in tension after 6 years of storage, a reduction in strength and stiffness was found, which could be attributed to either physical ageing and/or the gradual absorption of moisture promoting resin degradation. Thermal ageing (isothermal & thermal cycling) did not show any influence on the biaxial tensile specimens, however for tensile 90° specimens, a slight decrease in strain at IFF was observed. Concerning ILSS specimens, an increase in strength was observed due to isothermal ageing, while thermal shocks resulted in stiffness degradation, without a significant decrease in strength. Performed DSC measurements suggest that the effect of oxidation on the material during isothermal ageing can be excluded and changes in mechanical behaviour can possibly be attributed to physical ageing.

1 INTRODUCTION

During their operational life, wind turbines are exposed to severe atmospheric conditions. These conditions include extreme temperatures, humidity, salt environments, UV exposure, particle impact and rain erosion and contamination [1]. Therefore, the ageing and degradation of the composite materials used in wind turbines depend on a combination of these environmental (physical) loads in combination with mechanical (fatigue) loads and progressive damage interactions.

For determination of reliable composite material strength and fatigue properties, extensive characterization of various material properties is usually done under standard laboratory conditions. The ageing and degradation of composite materials is often accelerated by means of weathering equipment, in order to simulate natural ageing during operational conditions.

In order to understand the effect of temperature (physical ageing, chemical ageing and thermal stresses) on the degradation of these materials, it is important to describe and analyse these relevant damage mechanisms. Isothermal exposure of glass/epoxy materials to temperatures below glass transition temperature (T_g) for an extended period of time may cause physical ageing, consisting of molecular-level changes in the matrix material [2]. On the other hand, exposure to temperatures above T_g promotes chemical degradation (oxidation) of the material [3], particularly in oxygen-rich environments [4]. Both types of isothermal ageing tend to affect matrix-dominated mechanical properties. Another effect is initiated by thermal cycling, which can induce stresses and with that cracking inside the material by contraction/expansion of the glass and matrix material [5]. It is

important to note that material storage for long periods of time can also be seen as an isothermal ageing process at room temperature, which can potentially impact material mechanical properties.

This paper presents and analyses test data from strength and fatigue experiments on shelf-aged 6 years old material, as well as thermally aged material. For comparison, a selection of test standards was used to obtain material properties. Specimens extracted from panels manufactured between 2007 and 2014 are used to evaluate the effect of ageing during storage and after isothermal exposure. In order to investigate ageing during storage, UD and biaxial laminate specimens were tested in tension, compression and fatigue, both shortly after manufacturing as well as after approximately 6 years of laboratory storage without additional conditioning. For isothermal ageing, both the biaxial and UD laminates were conditioned for 720 hours at 60°C (~30°C below T_g) and tested statically and in fatigue. The biaxial specimens ($\pm 45^\circ$) were tested according to ISO 14129 (combination of tension and shear), and the UD laminates in short-beam shear (ISO 14130). Lastly, specimens were tested after being subjected to 100 thermal cycles from -40°C to 60°C and also to thermal shocks from 0°C to 100°C [6].

DSC measurements were performed to evaluate the effect of ageing on the T_g and enthalpy relaxation. Test results are compared with those from reference specimens. Then, the mechanisms responsible for matrix degradation during the ageing processes are discussed.

2 EXPERIMENTS

2.1 MATERIALS

E-glass/Epoxy composites are used in this work. This material is representative for wind turbine blades.

The resin system is the Momentive EPIKOTE RIMR 135 / EPIKURE RIMH 1366, consisting of a monomer (70-100% 4,4-Isopropylidenediphenol-Epichlorohydrin Copolymer and 0-30% 1,6-Hexanediol Diglycidyl Ether) and a hardener (25-50% Alkyletheramine, 20-25% Isophoronediamine and up to 20% Aminoethylpiperazine) [7], mixed in a 100:30 ratio between monomer and hardener.

On composite UD specimens, the Saertex PPG 2002 2400tex (963 g/m²) unidirectional fabric was used [8], featuring a silanic coupling agent in order to improve interface adhesion. On composite biaxial specimens, the Saertex PPG 2001 600tex (811 g/m²) biaxial fabric was used [9]. Composite panels with 4 and 6 plies (3mm and 4.5mm thick, respectively) were manufactured through vacuum infusion moulding. They were then post-cured for 10 hours at 70°C. For the UD panels, fibres were oriented in a single direction (0°) for 95% of the total areal weight of the fabric, with 90° stabilization roving (sr) being used, accounting for 5% of the total areal weight. The fabric is stacked with the side of the stability roving being alternated, resulting in a balanced and symmetric laminate [(sr / 0°) – (0° / sr)]_n, where n = 2 for the 4-ply laminate and n = 3 for the 6-ply one. For the biaxial panels, fibres were oriented bi-diagonally (+45° & -45°) each accounting for 50% of the total areal weight [(+45° / -45°) – (-45° / +45°)]₂. Specimens were cut from the panels using a CNC milling machine in order to maintain dimensional uniformity.

2.2 SPECIMENS

Short-beam shear specimens with geometry according to ISO 14130 [10] were cut from both the 4-ply and 6-ply UD laminates. Due to their short span, interlaminar shear failure is induced, and a measure of the fibre-matrix interfacial shear strength can be obtained.

Tensile 90° specimens with geometry based on ISO 527-5/B [11] were cut from 4-ply UD laminates. Due to a limited amount of available material, the specimens were scaled to 60% of the original geometry. The 90° orientation of the UD fibres results in a matrix dominated specimen, from which the inter-fibre failure strength can be obtained.

As for the UD and biaxial (tensile, compression and fatigue) tests, specimens with geometry according to the UPWIND reference geometries R08 (UD) & R09 (biaxial) and standard ASTM D3039 [12] were cut from 4-ply laminates (UD and biaxial, respectively). These geometries are suitable for static and fatigue tests at different loading conditions.

Biaxial tensile specimens with geometry according to ISO 14129 [13] were cut from 4 ply biaxial panels. Due to the $\pm 45^\circ$ orientation of the fabric a matrix dominated specimen is obtained from which in-plane shear parameters can be deduced.

2.3 SAMPLE CONDITIONING

The panels used in this study were manufactured between 2007 & 2014 in the scope of the UPWIND European research project. In order to investigate natural ageing during storage, a set of specimens was tested shortly after manufacturing as well as after approximately 6 years of laboratory storage without additional conditioning. The specimens tested shortly after manufacturing are used as reference data to compare with the set of naturally aged specimens.

A set of biaxial and UD specimens was isothermally conditioned for 720 hours at 60°C , which is approximately 30°C below the T_g of the resin system, after the initial period of natural ageing. The specimens were conditioned by means of an aluminium plate equipped with automated heating to control the temperature within $\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$. A second set of specimens was tested as reference material and therefore was not thermally conditioned.

In order to investigate the effect of thermal stresses inside the material, a set of biaxial and UD specimens was exposed to 100 thermal cycles from -40°C to 60°C with a cycle period of 4 hours (Figure 1). These thermal cycles were induced with a programmable Espec EGNX12-6CWL climate facility, which controls the air temperature within $\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. Additionally, a set of UD specimens was exposed to 10 & 100 thermal shocks from 0°C to 100°C . These thermal shocks were induced by submerging the specimens alternating between a bath of boiling water and a bath of ice water with a one minute submersion time for each bath.

An overview of all conditions in combination with the used specimen types can be found in Table 1.

Figure 1: Thermal cycle temperature/time profile.

Two DSC measurements were done to validate/exclude the effect of oxidation. Both samples were aged for 24 hours at 60°C , however one sample was aged in the absence of oxygen, in a pure nitrogen environment.

Material	Specimen type	Storage	Additional conditioning types		
			Isothermal	Thermal cycling	Thermal shock cycling
UD	R08 (0°)	6 years	–	–	–
UD	ILSS (0°)	6 years	720h at 60°C	100x -40 to +60°C	10x & 100x 0 to 100°C
UD	ISO 527-5/B (90°)	6 years	720h at 60°C	–	–
BX	R09 ($\pm 45^\circ$)	6 years	–	–	–
BX	ISO 14129 ($\pm 45^\circ$)		720h at 60°C	100x -40 to +60°C	–

Table 1: Conditioning overview

2.4 MECHANICAL TESTS

Composite biaxial specimens were tested in tension according to the ISO 14129 standard [13] in an Instron 25 kN test frame, as can be seen in Figure 2 (left). Static tests were conducted in displacement control at a speed of 2 mm/min until failure. Fatigue tests were also conducted in a tension-tension setup in load control at 1 Hz (high load level) to 6 Hz (low load level), with an R-value of 0.1.

Composite biaxial and UD 0° specimens were tested in tension and compression according to the UPWIND reference geometries and standard ASTM D3039 [12] in multiple standard hydraulic test frames. Static tests were conducted in displacement control at a speed of 1 mm/min until failure. Fatigue tests were conducted in a tension-compression (UD & biaxial) and a tension-tension (UD only) setup in load control at a frequency of 1 to 6 Hz, with R-values of -1 and 0.1 respectively.

Composite UD 0° specimens were tested in three-point bending according to the ISO 14130 standard [10] in a MTS 10kN test frame equipped with a three-point bending fixture, as can be seen in Figure 2 (right). Based on average specimen dimensions measured after cutting, the span of the fixture was fixed at 15.4 mm for specimens with 4 plies and 22.5 mm for specimens with 6 plies. For these tests only static tests were performed in displacement control at a speed of 1 mm/min until a significant load drop was observed.

Composite UD 90° specimens were tested in tension according to the ISO 527-5 standard [11] in an Instron 25 kN test frame, as can be seen in Figure 2 (left). Static tests were conducted in displacement control at a speed of 1 mm/min until failure.

Figure 2: Test setup for ISO 14129 & ISO 527-5/B (left) & ISO 14130 (right) specimens.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 UD R08 STATIC & FATIGUE NATURAL AGEING

In order to investigate the influence of ageing during storage on the composite material, strength and fatigue experiments were performed on specimens made from panels manufactured in 2007. Shortly after manufacturing, UD 0° specimens were tested in tension, compression and fatigue. Figure 3 shows the stress-strain curves for the specimens tested in tension and compression. From the compression results, no significant degradation in strength and stiffness can be observed. In Table 2 however, for tension the average maximum stress suffers a decrease of approximately 8%. Also the measured stiffness is about 7% lower compared to the reference tests. Such decreases fall in line with literature results on physical ageing [2, 14], and can possibly be related to micro-crack growth brought by resin embrittlement during ageing. However, as the ageing occurred at room temperature, only small contributions from physical ageing are expected. It is also possible that, during storage, moisture was gradually absorbed by the panels, which were exposed to a relative humidity value of approximately 50%. This seems to be coherent with the results from an associated research project on hydrothermal ageing [15], where water absorption promotes degradation on fibre-matrix interface performance, with a significant reduction in strength. In any case, it is important to note that most observed changes are within statistical uncertainty and therefore require further investigation.

Figure 3: Stress-strain plots for UD tension (left) & compression (right).

		Reference	Natural ageing
Tension			
F_{\max}	[kN]	53.2 ± 1.8	51.1 ± 2.8
σ_{\max}	[MPa]	908 ± 40	835 ± 47
ε_{\max}	[%]	2.6 ± 0.17	2.6 ± 0.17
E_1	[GPa]	38.3 ± 1.2	35.5 ± 0.7
ν_{12}	–	0.261 ± 0.017	0.262 ± 0.010
Compression			
F_{\max}	[kN]	32.6 ± 1.1	33.9 ± 1.6
σ_{\max}	[MPa]	557 ± 18	559 ± 29
ε_{\max}	[%]	1.50 ± 0.10	1.53 ± 0.06
E_1	[GPa]	37.4 ± 0.9	36.2 ± 0.8
ν_{12}	–	–	0.265 ± 0.009

Table 2: UD tension & compression data

The SN-curves for the UD specimens in fatigue can be seen in Figure 4. The tension-tension ($R = 0.1$) fatigue plot shows little difference between both regression lines (Equations 1 & 2). The curve for the aged tension-compression ($R = -1$) fatigue tests shows a decrease in fatigue life of one order of magnitude at approximately 400 MPa. While at a load level of 230 MPa no significant difference is observed. This caused the slope of the curve to flatten slightly (Equations 3 & 4). No obvious correlation was found between this difference in fatigue life and the static values. Since tests were done at a high and low load level only, it is recommended to perform more tests at intermediate load levels to confirm the regression line.

$$\text{Reference: } \log N = -10.1 \cdot \log S + 31.5 \quad (\text{st.dev.} = 0.215) \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Natural: } \log N = -8.44 \cdot \log S + 26.9 \quad (\text{st.dev.} = 0.444) \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Reference: } \log N = -8.75 \cdot \log S + 26.7 \quad (\text{st.dev.} = 0.269) \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Natural: } \log N = -11.3 \cdot \log S + 32.4 \quad (\text{st.dev.} = 0.337) \quad (4)$$

Figure 4: SN-curves for UD fatigue $R = -1$ (left) & $R = 0.1$ (right).

3.2 BIAxIAL R09 FATIGUE NATURAL AGEING

Figure 5 (left) shows the SN-curve for the biaxial specimens tested in tension-compression fatigue. These tests were conducted to further investigate the influence of storage on the glass/epoxy material. Since the mechanical behaviour of biaxial specimens is matrix dominated and because the resin material is more susceptible to degradation, these tests were conducted to assess if 6 years of storage influences the material properties. Although the plot shows a difference in slope (Equations 5 & 6) of the regression lines, no significant degradation in fatigue life was observed.

$$\text{Reference: } \log N = -12.8 \cdot \log S + 26.2 \quad (\text{st.dev.} = 0.387) \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Natural: } \log N = -18.9 \cdot \log S + 37.0 \quad (\text{st.dev.} = 0.289) \quad (6)$$

Figure 5: SN-curves for biaxial fatigue (R09) R = -1 (left) & (ISO 14129) R = 0.1 (right)

3.3 BIAxIAL ISO 14129 STATIC & FATIGUE ISOTHERMAL & THERMAL CYCLING

The results for ISO 14129 tensile tests can be seen in Figure 6 (left) and Table 3, where values for reference, isothermally aged & thermally cycled specimens are compared. No influence was found of subjecting the material to isothermal conditioning below T_g or thermal cycling according to the temperature profile shown in Figure 1. Also for fatigue (Figure 5; right) thermal ageing did not show any effect on the fatigue life of the composite (Equations 7 to 9).

$$\text{Reference:} \quad \log N = -10.0 \cdot \log S + 23.4 \quad (\text{st.dev.} = 0.193) \quad (7)$$

$$\text{Isothermal:} \quad \log N = -9.67 \cdot \log S + 22.7 \quad (\text{st.dev.} = 0.126) \quad (8)$$

$$\text{Thermal cycling:} \quad \log N = -9.05 \cdot \log S + 21.6 \quad (\text{st.dev.} = 0.208) \quad (9)$$

Figure 6: Stress-displacement plots for biaxial tension (ISO 14129) (left) & UD tension 90° (right)

		Reference	Isothermal	Thermal cycling
F_{\max}	[kN]	8.92 ± 0.24	9.03 ± 0.30	8.91 ± 0.16
σ_{\max}	[MPa]	141 ± 3	142 ± 3	139 ± 2
$\sigma_{0.2}$	[MPa]	65.2 ± 1.3	65.5 ± 1.8	64.3 ± 1.2
$\varepsilon_{0.2}$	[%]	0.75 ± 0.01	0.77 ± 0.01	0.76 ± 0.01
E_1	[GPa]	11.7 ± 0.2	11.3 ± 0.4	11.3 ± 0.4
ν_{12}	–	0.588 ± 0.009	0.600 ± 0.010	0.594 ± 0.018
τ_{\max}	[MPa]	70.3 ± 1.6	70.8 ± 1.7	69.4 ± 1.1
$\tau_{5\%}$	[MPa]	47.9 ± 1.0	50.4 ± 2.6	48.4 ± 0.7
$\tau_{0.2}$	[MPa]	29.3 ± 0.5	29.2 ± 0.9	28.7 ± 0.7
$\gamma_{0.2}$	[%]	1.01 ± 0.01	1.04 ± 0.01	1.02 ± 0.02
G	[GPa]	3.43 ± 0.06	3.32 ± 0.12	3.32 ± 0.14

Table 3: Biaxial static tension data

3.4 UD ISO 527-5/B STATIC TENSION 90° ISOTHERMAL

To investigate the effect of temperature on the interaction between the glass fibre and the epoxy, tests were conducted according to ISO 527-5, Type B. An important value gathered from these tests is the inter-fibre-failure transverse tensile strength (IFF) which corresponds to the first drop in load in the stress-displacement curve (Figure 6; right). The IFF strain values were slightly lower for the isothermally aged specimens (Table 4), agreeing with observed decreases due to physical ageing in literature [2, 14].

		Reference	Isothermal
F_{\max}	[kN]	3.38 ± 0.36	3.89 ± 0.19
σ_{\max}	[MPa]	75.4 ± 8.0	86.8 ± 0.15
ε_{\max}	[%]	1.74 ± 0.18	1.92 ± 0.15
F_{IFF}	[kN]	1.76 ± 0.15	1.79 ± 0.09
σ_{IFF}	[MPa]	39.2 ± 3.4	39.9 ± 1.9
ε_{IFF}	[%]	0.39 ± 0.12	0.31 ± 0.02
E_1	[GPa]	12.4 ± 0.4	12.9 ± 0.3
ν_{12}	–	0.085 ± 0.002	0.094 ± 0.003

Table 4: UD tension 90° data

3.5 UD ISO 14130 ILSS ISOTHERMAL & THERMAL (SHOCK) CYCLING

To research the influence of temperature on the fibre-matrix interfacial shear strength, inter-laminar shear tests were performed. Within this project, two different panel thicknesses (4 & 6 ply) were used to also investigate the influence of specimen scaling with different weathering conditions. Figure 7 & Table 5 show the results for the ILSS testing performed after different conditioning types. Figure 7 (left) shows the results for the 4 ply specimens, where a significant increase in strength is observed for both the isothermal and thermal cycling conditioning. In Figure 7 (right) the graph for the 6 ply specimens shows a small increase in strength for the thermally cycles samples, while the thermal shock cycled samples show a slight decrease in strength as well as a decrease in stiffness.

Such increases in strength agree with literature results on the effects of physical ageing [2], where improved material performance in shear was observed after prolonged periods of exposure to sub- T_g temperatures. The fact that a similar behaviour was obtained after thermal cycling can be possibly explained considering that the adopted cycle included multiple periods of isothermal exposure at the same temperature adopted in the isothermal case. The combined influence of such isothermal periods may have led to a material molecular structure similar to the one obtained after pure isothermal conditioning [6].

Regarding the effect of thermal shocks, the observed stiffness degradation may be attributed to debonding brought by the rapid variation of thermal stresses during the exposure. However, as a low exposure time was adopted (1 minute for each temperature), it is likely that, due to heat diffusion mechanics, the centre of the specimen did not experience significant degradation. The specimen centre is also the region with the highest shear stress. Such considerations may explain the fact that the strength did not suffer significant degradation after conditioning. Since the measurements for the specimens exposed to 10 & 100 thermal shocks show similar results, they were presented together in Figure 7 & Table 5.

		Reference	Isothermal	Thermal cycling	Thermal shock
4 plies					
F_{max}	[kN]	2.82 ± 0.07	3.18 ± 0.10	3.06 ± 0.06	–
τ_{max}	[MPa]	45.6 ± 1.0	51.2 ± 1.5	50.6 ± 0.6	–
6 plies					
F_{max}	[kN]	6.23 ± 0.19	–	6.57 ± 0.05	6.09 ± 0.05
τ_{max}	[MPa]	46.0 ± 1.3	–	48.8 ± 0.4	45.1 ± 0.4

Table 5: UD ILSS data

Figure 7: UD ILSS isothermal & thermal (shock) cycling plots

3.6 GLASS TRANSITION TEMPERATURE MEASUREMENTS

Two DSC (Differential Scanning Calorimetry) measurements were done to investigate the possible occurrence of oxidative reactions during conditioning (see Figure 8). At first, both samples were thermally rejuvenated by heating them for 10 minutes at 130°C, erasing their thermal history [2]. After this erasure cycle, each sample was aged for 24 hours at 60°C. One sample was conditioned by means of an aluminium plate equipped with automated heating, the same setup used for isothermal conditioning. This sample was exposed to a standard 80/20 nitrogen/oxygen environment. The other sample was conditioned inside the DSC machine, in the absence of oxygen, in a pure nitrogen environment, created by a constant flow of nitrogen (50ml/min) along the sample.

After the 24h ageing period, the glass transition temperature (T_g) was determined for both samples, by performing two consecutive measurement cycles up to 130°C (20°C/min). The first cycle presents the T_g of the aged material (red & blue curves in Figure 8), while the second cycle gives the reference value of the material (black curves in Figure 8).

Figure 8: T_g after isothermal ageing (24h; 60°C) with oxygen (blue) & without (red).

The T_g values in Figure 8 show no significant differences when comparing conditioning with or without the presence of oxygen. This suggests that the effect of oxidation on the material during isothermal ageing in the aluminium plate is negligible. Physical ageing can thus be regarded as the driving force of the observed mechanical behaviour changes. However more tests are needed to confirm these results, as only one sample was used for each case.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This work investigated the effect of and relation between ageing and temperature on the static and fatigue mechanical properties of wind turbine composite materials. In order to describe and analyse the relevant damage mechanisms of these materials, specimens were exposed to different types of conditioning environments. Specimens stored for 6 years were compared with reference results, obtained from tests performed shortly after manufacturing, regarding static tension, compression and fatigue properties. Also, specimens isothermally conditioned (30°C below T_g) for an extended period of time, as well as specimens subjected to thermal cycling and thermal shock, were compared with reference data.

For the UD tension 0° specimens tested in tension after 6 years of storage, a reduction in strength and stiffness was found, which could be attributed to either physical ageing related to micro-crack growth brought by resin embrittlement and/or the gradual absorption of moisture promoting resin degradation. For tension-compression fatigue tests on these specimens, no clear correlation was found between the decrease in fatigue life at a high load level and the static values. Further research is necessary to isolate the mechanism involved with this degradation of fatigue life.

Thermal ageing (isothermal & thermal cycling) did not show any influence on the biaxial tensile specimens considering both static and fatigue performance. On the tensile 90° specimens however, a slight decrease in strain at IFF was observed, which is in line with observed decreases due to physical ageing in literature. Concerning the ILSS specimens, the increase in strength is also in agreement with literature about physical ageing, where improved material performance in shear was observed after prolonged periods of exposure to sub- T_g temperatures. Thermal shock cycling resulted in stiffness degradation, which may be attributed to debonding brought by the rapid variation of thermal stresses

during the exposure. No significant decrease in strength was observed, which can be explained by the fact that limited heat diffusion into the centre of the specimen, which experiences the highest shear stresses, prevented the material there from undergoing significant degradation.

DSC measurements were performed to investigate the possible occurrence of oxidative reactions during conditioning. From these measurements, no significant differences were observed, suggesting that the effect of oxidation on the material during isothermal ageing can be excluded and changes in mechanical behaviour can be explained by physical ageing.

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